

Canine Parvo Virus

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Introduction

All dogs are susceptible to the highly contagious canine parvovirus, but puppies under four months old and unvaccinated dogs are most at risk. The term "parvo" is frequently used to describe canine parvovirus infections that cause illness. Although most Parvoviruses are species-specific, parvoviruses are small, non-enveloped, single-stranded DNA viruses that are known to infect a variety of mammalian species. Parvovirus binds to the host cell by the double-stranded ends of the genome and needs the host cell for replication, more specifically the cell nucleus. Viral replication occurs only in rapidly dividing cells such as intestinal crypt epithelial cells, precursor cells in the bone marrow, and myocardiocytes. Viral replication result in cell death and loss due to failure of mitosis. Not all fast-dividing cell populations are equally affected, suggesting a viral tropism for certain target organs.

The virus mainly affects dog's gastrointestinal tracts (GIT) and is spread by direct dog to dog contact and contact with contaminated faeces (stool), environments, or people. The virus can also contaminate food and water bowls, kennel surfaces, leashes and collars, and the hands and clothing of people who handle infected dogs. It is resistant to humidity, heat, cold and drying and can survive in the environment for long period of time. Even trace amount of faeces from an infected dog may harbor the virus and infect other dogs that come into the infected environment. The virus is readily transmitted from place to place on the feet or hair of dogs or via contaminated shoes, cages, or other objects.

Clinical signs

Lethargy, loss of appetite, abdominal pain and bloating, fever or low body temperature (hypothermia), vomiting, and severe, frequently bloody diarrhoea are some of the symptoms of

parvovirus. Intestinal and immune system damage can result in septic shock, and persistent vomiting and diarrhoea can quickly cause dehydration. The majority of parvovirus deaths happen 48 to 72 hours after the onset of clinical symptoms. The moment your dog or puppy exhibits any of these symptoms, you should

call your veterinarian.

Diagnosis

Canine parvovirus fulminant cases are relatively simple to diagnose. The combination of acute enteritis, fever, and leukopenia is a rare occurrence in canine illnesses. The best way to establish a definitive diagnosis is to show canine parvovirus in the stool, which is a relatively simple task in acute cases due to the amount of virus present. Diagnostic laboratories have access to a variety of techniques, including stool hemagglutination, electron microscopy, and others. An ELISA test performed in-office is possibly the most practical method for practitioners. (Cite test, IDDEXX, 560 POLLOCK & COYNE Portland, ME).

Treatment

There isn't a specific medication that can kill the virus in infected dogs, so the goal of treatment is to support the body systems of the dog until its immune system can eradicate the viral infection. The primary goals of treatment, which should begin right away, are to combat dehydration by replenishing electrolyte, protein, and fluid losses, managing vomiting and diarrhea,

and avoiding secondary infections. Dogs that are ill should be kept warm and given expert nursing care. Even with aggressive treatment, a dog with parvo may not survive and treatment for it can be very expensive. Successful outcomes heavily depend on early detection and aggressive treatment. Survival rates can approach 90% with the right care.

Since parvovirus is extremely contagious, it is essential to isolate infected dogs in order to prevent infection from spreading. Controlling the spread of parvovirus requires thorough cleaning and disinfection of contaminated kennels and other locations where infected dogs are (or have been) housed. Because the virus is difficult to eradicate, speak with your veterinarian for advice on the best cleaning and disinfecting solutions.

Prevention

Vaccination and well hygiene are critical components of prevention.

Young puppies are particularly vulnerable to infection because their mothers' milk's natural immunity may wear off before the puppies' own immune systems are developed enough to combat

infection. Puppy illness is possible if canine parvovirus exposure occurs during this time of reduced immunity. Another issue is that a mother's milk's immunity may prevent a newborn from responding to a vaccination effectively. This means that even puppies who have received vaccinations may occasionally contract the parvovirus and become ill. A series of puppy vaccinations are given in order to minimise protection gaps and offer the best protection against parvovirus during the first few months of life. Regardless of how many doses they had previously received, puppies should receive a dose of the canine parvovirus vaccine between the ages of 14 and 16 weeks old in order to develop an adequate protection.

Owners of adult dogs should ensure that their dogs are up to date on their parvovirus vaccinations in order to protect them. The amount of antibodies a dog has against the canine parvovirus can be measured using titers, but exposure to the virus may not necessarily result in protection. Inquire with your vet about the best prevention plan for your dog.

When bringing their pet to areas where young puppies congregate, pet owners should exercise caution until their pet has received the full series of vaccinations (e.g. kennels, pet shops, puppy classes, parks, obedience classes, doggy daycare, and grooming establishments). By requiring vaccinations, health checks, good hygiene, and isolation of sick puppies and dogs, respectable facilities and training programmes lower the risk of exposure. Always avoid coming into contact with known infected dogs and their properties. A small percentage of dogs do not develop protective immunity and remain susceptible to infection even after receiving the recommended vaccinations.

Don't let your puppy or adult dog to come into contact with the fecal waste of other dogs while walking or playing outdoors. It is always advisable to dispose of waste materials promptly and properly in order to prevent the spread of diseases that can affect both humans and animals, such as the canine parvovirus infection.

It is advisable to keep sick dogs away from kennels, dog parks, show grounds, and other places where they may interact with other dogs. This also applies to dogs who have been exposed to sick animals. The same goes for unvaccinated dogs they shouldn't be exposed to sick or unvaccinated dogs. The handling of other dogs should be avoided by people who have been in

contact with sick or exposed dogs, or at the very least, they should wash their hands and change their clothes before doing so.

References

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